

The Influence of The Talking Stick Method on The German Speaking Ability of Class XI Students at Tamansiswa Private High School Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to see the effect of the Talking Stick method on the speaking abilities of class XI students at Tamansiswa Pematang Private High School Siantar. The research method used is Quantitative with Pre-experimental And design study One Group Pretest-Posttest. Population study namely class XI Tamansiswa Private High School Pematang Siantar with 125 people. Based on Purposive sampling technique, from the population produced 30 people, namely class XI IPA-4 as research sample. The data collection techniques that is form test b text speaks German. By doing steps pretest, treatment by applying the method learning Talking Stick And posttest so generated data study. The average pretest score is 56.67 which is included in the category not good then the average posttest result is 80.00 which is included in the category very Good. Based on results analysis data And hypothesis Which tested, is known that There was an increase in the German speaking skills of class XI students at Tamansiswa Private High School Pematang Siantar with Talking Stick method . Matter This is proven by the results of the normality test analysis with a pre-test score of 0.085 ($0.05 < 0.085$) and the posttest score was 0.173 ($0.05 < 0.173$). Then based on the test hypothesis statistics with paired samples test generated mark significance as big as $0.001 < 0.05$ in meaning of calculated statistical results (number t output) < table statistics (t-table), concluded that H_0 rejected And H_1 accepted . With thereby there is skill improvement speak the language German student class XI Tamansiswa Pematang Private High School Siantar by applying the Talking stick method to class XI IPA-4 students.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era, language plays an important role in society because through language we can communicate with fellow humans so that we can communicate in conveying our intentions and goals to other people. Nowadays, with increasingly sophisticated technology, humans are required to be able to interact and learn information using foreign languages. Everyone can master the ability to communicate using a foreign language properly and correctly. Regarding communication, language is an important aspect. Chaer (2018) stated that language is the only possession of humans throughout human existence. Then Rohmadi et al (2015:52) explained that language has a function, namely as a communication tool in various contexts, both verbal and written.

In Indonesia, foreign languages have an important role and great influence both in carrying out state cooperation relations, as well as carrying out further education in other countries that use language as a means of communication. In this way, foreign languages are used as formal lessons, namely in the teaching and learning process. This is done to improve the quality of education in Indonesia.

German generally has four skills, namely; reading skills (*Leseverstehen*), writing skills (*Schreibfertigkeit*), listening skills (*Hörverstehen*), speaking skills (*Sprechfertigkeit*). These four skills must have equal portions, therefore they can be said to be effective and communicative. Learning German aims to ensure that students are able to communicate well orally and in writing in German and are able to get to know German culture. In accordance with the following objectives, German speaking skills in teaching must be further improved.

German at the high school level is one of the subjects in specialization classes, several schools have collaborations with the German government, learning German at the high school level certainly has learning achievements. In the learning process, strategies, techniques, models and learning methods are needed that can help in the effectiveness of learning.

The researcher's observations during PPL in class This is thought to be due to several aspects that can influence students' interest in learning so that they are less motivated to learn German, and also the limited vocabulary that students have, then students' understanding of German grammar is very minimal, for example the students' speaking skills are still very minimal. Of course, another obstacle is caused by the lack of application of less active German language learning methods, so that students are very less able to improve their ability to speak German.

The German language curriculum must provide learning experiences that involve students in learning that can increase student creativity. It is hoped that the approach used in the curriculum will encourage students to be active and flexible. Specifically this approach will:

1. Pay attention to students' individual differences.
2. provide opportunities for all students to learn essential concepts.
3. Equipping students with the skills to understand the world through inquiry and research.

4. Equip students with the skills to select appropriate tools and necessary materials.

Based on the competency standard syllabus listed in the 2013 curriculum, speaking skills require students to be able to express information orally with correct pronunciation in simple sentences and in the form of simple explanations or dialogues. As a language skill, speaking has characteristics like other language skills.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The Facts of Learning German as a Foreign Language

Foreign language learning is an activity carried out to obtain knowledge and information. Language is a tool for communicating with fellow humans. According to Brown (2005:5) it is stated "Language is a system of arbitrary conventionalized vocal, written or gestural symbols that enable members of a given community to communicate intelligently with one another".

According to Kinneavy (in Chaer, 2009: 33) argues that language has five basic functions, namely the function of expression, information function, explorative function, persuasion function and entertainment function.

So students must be able to understand the culture that exists in a country. Therefore, students are able to understand ethics culture adopted by that country. Students are able to more easily use a language adopted by that country properly and correctly, one of which is German.

The Nature of Speaking Skills

According to Djiwandono (2008:118) states that speaking means expressing thoughts verbally. Speaking is a daily activity that a person carries out in communicating with other people in various activities. Developing a person's speaking ability requires appropriate methods so that a person is able to interact with their environment. Nurgiantoro (2010:399) states that speaking is the second language activity that humans carry out in language life after listening. Based on this statement, the sounds that are heard, then a person learns to express them so that the person is able to speak, according to Nurgiantoro (2010: 397) states that speaking activities are generally activities that give and receive language, in speaking expresses a person's messages and ideas to interlocutors at the same time.

The Nature of German Speaking Skills

We can conclude that speaking is an activity carried out in communicating with other people. So from there we know that speaking skills are very important for students to learn at school in order to gain insight into something new, so that students are also more accustomed to conveying their ideas through speaking more actively.

Efforts made to improve students' speaking skills which are considered still lacking are necessary done an application of the method for students to improve their German speaking skills. Things that teachers need to do to train

students to speak by using German , then the teacher must also provide more dialogue to students to become more trained in speaking German.

Table 2.1 Achievement of Speaking Ability

Basic competencies	Indicators achieved
2.1 Convey information orally with correct pronunciation in simple sentences according to the context that reflects polite and appropriate language skills	2.1.1. Say German words related to family themes with correct pronunciation and intonation. 2.1.2. Carrying out questions and answers orally in simple sentences according to context. 2.1.3. Convey information orally in simple sentences according to context.
2.2. Carrying out simple dialogue, fluently, which reflects polite and appropriate communication skills	2.2.1. Carrying out simple questions and answers about the use of accusative personal pronouns fluently and communicatively with the available vocabulary. 2.2.2. Conduct simple interviews that reflect communicating politely and fluently about the use of accusative personal pronouns.

Assessment of German Speaking Skills

In this research, the German speaking skills research type uses an assessment of speaking skills based on criteria according to Reinmann (1998:64), the forms of the test are as follows:

a. *Ausdrucksfähigkeit*

Assess aspects such as how students express themselves using familiar expressions, as well as students' ability to master vocabulary.

b. *Aufgabenbewältigung*

Assess how students solve problems, activeness in speaking and students' understanding of what they express.

c. *Formal Richtigkeit*

Assessing the correct and incorrect grammar used by students or students' mastery in applying German language structure and grammar.

d. Aussprache und Intonation

Assessing students' pronunciation and intonation in speaking German. Based on the above research aspects, the German speaking skills test has been adapted to the curriculum that applies at high school level, the assessment of German speaking skills is based on criteria according to Reinmann because there are components that are considered easy in assessing German speaking skills.

Table 2.2 Assesment Test Skills Speak

Aspect	Mark	Criteria
<i>Ausdruckfähigkeit</i>	25	Students' abilities in disclose with style Language very Good. Students' abilities in disclose with style Language Good. Students' abilities in disclose with style Language Enough Good. Students' abilities in disclose with style Language bad. Students' abilities in disclose with style Language very bad.
<i>Aufgabenbewältigung</i>	25	Liveliness And understanding participant educate very Good. Liveliness And understanding participant educate Good. Liveliness And understanding participant educate Enough Good. Liveliness And understanding participant educate bad. Liveliness And understanding participant educate very bad.
<i>Formal Richtigkeit</i>	25	No There is or seldom do error structure grammatical Language German. A little do error structure grammatical Language German. A number of time do error structure grammatical Language German. Lots of structural errors grammatical Language German. Very Lots do error structure grammatical Language German.
<i>Aussprache und Intonation</i>	25	Error in pronunciation And intonation No bother understanding. Error in pronunciation And intonation A

	little bother understanding. Error in pronunciation And intonation Enough bother understanding. Error in pronunciation And intonation very bother understanding.
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The Nature of the Talking Stick Method

Talking Stick learning method is a form of cooperative learning method that invites students to learn actively using tools in the form of sticks. The Talking Stick learning method is learning using a tool in the form of a stick which triggers students to be more active in expressing opinions and suggestions using a rolling stick. Talking sticks are effective in learning activities and meaningful for students. Talking sticks can grow students' courage in telling stories about experiences by using a tool in the form of a talking stick which is moved from one student to another, as a marker for speaking turns. By using this talking stick method students can learn while playing without feeling stiff and tense.

Applying the talking stick method correctly can have a good effect on students and ultimately can have a good effect on learning indicators. So in this research the method applied is the talking stick method because it can help students be more active. This will increase students' ability to be active in speaking, then this can make teaching and learning activities in class easier and learning will not feel boring.

Figure 2.1. Framework of Thought

METHODS

The type of research contained in this research is quantitative research. The research design used in this research is Pre-test and Post-Test Design . This design is carried out twice in one class, namely before and after treatment. Pre-test (O_1) before carrying out treatment t and Post-Test (O_2) after carrying out treatment . The results of this pre-test and post-test treatment can be seen as to the influence of the Talking Stick learning method on the speaking abilities of class XI students at Tamansiswa Private High School Pematang Siantar.

Table 3.1 Pre-Test and Post-Test Research Design

<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>
O_1	X	O_2

Information:

O_1 = Pre-Test Score (Speaking ability before using the method
Talking Stick Learning .

X = Treatment uses the Talking Stick learning method .

O_2 = Post-Test Score (speaking ability after using the method
Talking Stick Learning .

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that this research was presented from the Pre-test (O_1) presented in the experimental class before being given Treatment (X). then the research process carried out was by providing treatment (Treatment) , namely to apply the Talking Stick learning method in class It will be seen from changes in students' speaking abilities, whether students' abilities have increased or there has been no change.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

In this research experimental class, there were 30 students. One Group Pretest and Posttest Design research. In one class the experiment was carried out twice, namely before and after treatment without a control class. The results of the pretest and posttest treatment can be seen how effective the talking stick method is on the speaking skills of class XI students at Tamansiswa Private High School Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Speaking Skills Pretest

N	Valid	30
	Missing	0
Mean		56.67
Median		55.00
Mode		55
Std. Deviation		9,034
Variance		81,609
Range		35
Minimum		35
Maximum		70
Sum		1700

(source: IBM SPSS 29 For Windows)

Table 4.1 shows that the total data for class XI IPA-4 as an experimental class is 30 students (N= 30). The total of all data divided by the amount of data determined as the pretest average (Mean) value is 56.67. The Median data is 55.00, the Variance value is 81,609, the standard deviation (Std. Deviation) is 9,034, the Mode value is 55. and the total number of numbers in the sum data is 1700.

Table 4.2. Descriptive Statistical Data Analysis

Posttest Speaking Skills

N	Valid	30
	Missing	0
Mean		80.00
Median		80.00
Mode		80

Std. Deviation	7,768
Variance	60,345
Range	30
Minimum	65
Maximum	95
Sum	2400

Source: IBM SPSS For Windows

The table shows that the total data for class XI IPA 4 as an experimental class is 30 students. The average value (Mean) of the pretest is 80.00, the lowest value (Minimum) is 65 then the highest value (Maximum) is 95, and the middle value (Median) is 80.00, the variance value is 60.345, the standard deviation (Std . Deviation) amounted to 7,768, for the mode value (Mode) was 80. and the total number of numbers in the data (Sum) was 2400. So it was concluded from the results of the average posttest score that there was an increase in the grades of class XI IPA-4 students regarding speaking ability. . So there is an influence of the Talking Stick method on the ability to speak German in class XI IPA students at Tamansiswa Private High School Pematang Siantar.

Normality test

Normal, if the significant value is greater than 0.05 at ($P > 0.05$). Conversely, if the significant value is smaller than 0.05 at ($P < 0.05$) then the data is said to be abnormal.

Table 4.3 Tests of Normality

	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
Speaking Skills Pretest	,939	30	,085
Posttest Speaking Skills	,950	30	.173

The normality test is a test carried out as a prerequisite for carrying out data analysis. The normality test is used to determine whether the research data obtained is normally distributed, good data is data that resembles a normal distribution. The data normality test aims to detect the distribution of data in one variable that will be used in research. The normality test used is IBM SPSS 29 for Windows. The data is said to be based on the Shapiro-Wilk test, the data is declared to be normally distributed if sig. the score is above 0.05. The Shapiro-Wilk table using the Lilliefors significance correction above shows that the pretest and posttest questions are normally distributed. The pre-test score was 0.085 ($0.05 < 0.062$) and the post-test score was 0.179 ($0.05 < 0.179$).

Hypothesis testing

After carrying out a normality test and proving that the data is normally distributed, then proceed with hypothesis testing. Hypothesis testing is a procedure that leads to a decision, namely the decision to accept or reject the hypothesis. Hypothesis testing aims to detect significant differences between the results before and after the test and to determine the effect of the Talking Stick Method on the speaking ability of class XI students at Tamansiswa Private High School Pematang Siantar. The hypothesis test used in this research is the paired sample t-test. This test is used based on the nature of the sample, namely paired samples, which means the same sample but has two data. The hypothesis test uses criteria with a significance level of 5% (0.05). So it can be concluded whether there has been an increase in the German speaking skills of class XI students at Tamansiswa Private High School Pematang Siantar.

Table 4.4. Paired Sample Test

Source: IBM SPSS *for windows*

Paired Samples Test					
Paired Differences		Significance			
95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Q	Df	One-Sided p	Two-Sided p
Lower	Upper				
-24,831	-21,835	-31,859	29	<.001	<.001

The hypotheses of this research are as follows:

1. H₀: There is no improvement in the German speaking skills of class XI IPASMA Private Tamansiswa Pematang Siantar students with the influence of the *Talking Stick method*.
2. H₁: There are German speaking skills in class XI IPA students at Tamansiswa Pematang Siantar Private High School with the influence of the *Talking Stick Method*.

A study is said to have a proven hypothesis if the significance value is less than 0.05 (sig. < 0.05), where H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Based on table 4.4, it can be seen that the significance value in hypothesis testing using the SPSS Statistics program version 29 for Windows obtained a significance value of <0.001. Thus the research hypothesis can be considered supported by the fact that <0.001 of 0.05. This shows that there is quite a big difference between students who received learning influenced by the Talking Stick method and students who received learning without using talking sticks in their speaking skills. This shows that the influence of the talking stick method can improve the speaking skills of class XI students at Tamansiswa Private

High School Pematang Siantar. In the sense that the calculated statistical results (T output numbers) > table statistics (T table) then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted.

Discussion

This research aims to find out whether there is an improvement in the German speaking skills of class XI IPA students at Tamansiswa Pematang Siantar Private High School with the influence of the Talking Stick method. The type of research carried out was a pre-experimental design with the One Group Pretest - Posttest Design type. The population in this study was the entire class XI of Tamansiswa Private High School Pematang Siantar with a sample of only one class, namely class

At the research implementation stage, before the researcher gave an initial test (pretest) to measure the level of students' speaking skills before being given treatment, the researcher first taught the grammar of the pretest questions, then provided treatment, namely by applying the Talking Stick during learning. And then give a final test (posttest) to measure the improvement in students' reading skills after being given treatment.

After the research stage was completed, the researcher analyzed the data on the pretest and posttest results. The pretest table shows the total of all data divided by the amount of data determined as the pretest average value is 56.67. The data that is located in the middle after being sorted according to numbers is determined as the median score is 55. The element that appears most frequently in the set of elements designated as the mode score is 55. The standard deviation score is 9.034. The sum of the squares of the differences between the observation data values and the average score, then divided by the number of observations determined by the variance score, is 81.609. The highest score from the pretest questions was 70 and the lowest was 35. The total score obtained was 1700. The average posttest score was 80.00. The data that is located in the middle after being sorted according to the number determined as the median score is 80.00. The element that appears most frequently in the set of elements is determined as the mode score is 80. The standard deviation score is 7.768. The sum of the squares of the differences between the observation data values and the average score, then divided by the number of observations determined by the variance score, is 60,345. The highest score from the posttest questions is 95 and the lowest is 65. The total score obtained is 2400. It can be concluded that the average posttest score is higher than the pretest score.

After the pretest and posttest data are known, a normality test is carried out. The normality test is used to determine whether the research data obtained is normally distributed. The pretest score was 0.085 ($0.05 < 0.085$) and the posttest score was 0.173 ($0.05 < 0.173$). Therefore the data is said to be normally distributed.

The results of the paired sample t-test obtained a significance value of 0.001, so it was concluded that it was smaller than 0.05, meaning there was a significant influence. In the sense that the calculated statistical results (T output numbers) > table statistics (T table) then H_0 is rejected. H_1 is accepted.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of data analysis and hypothesis testing, researchers put forward the following conclusions: The average score for students' reading skills after the treatment (posttest) was 80.00 , and the average score before the treatment (pretest) was 5.6.67 . It was concluded that the average posttest score was higher than the pretest score, meaning that there was an increase in the speaking skills of class XI IPA 4 students at Tamansiswa Private High School Pematang Siantar using the Talking Stick method . This is proven by the results of the paired sample t-test, which obtained a significance value of <0.001 , so it was concluded that it was smaller than 0.05, meaning there was a significant influence. In the sense that the calculated statistical results (T output numbers) $>$ table statistics (T table) then H_0 is rejected. H_1 is accepted.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions put forward by the researcher, the researcher puts forward the following suggestions:

It is hoped that it can contribute to students, especially students at Tmansiswa Pematang Siantar Private High School, that the Talking Stick method can improve students' speaking skills, so that student learning outcomes are better. It is hoped that it can make a contribution to educators or prospective educators, that the Talking Stick method can be applied to improve students' speaking skills.

This research should be used by other researchers who wish to conduct further research.

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